

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

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RDA for Agricultural Data

Celebrating A Decade of Data
RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop

Version: December 2022

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

The community cross-fertilisation workshop, 'RDA for Agricultural Data', brought chairs and members of the RDA Improving Global Agricultural Data (IGAD) Community of Practice together, with members of the wider research data community, to share and discuss challenges, solutions and initiatives associated with managing agricultural data. The key findings of the workshop summarised herein will be used to direct the future strategy of the RDA community. Read more about the [community cross-fertilisation workshop series](#) in commemoration of the [RDA's 10th Anniversary](#).

CHALLENGES TO BE ADDRESSED WITHIN THE THEME OF AGRICULTURAL DATA

Diversity of data types & sources

- The heterogeneity of agricultural sub-disciplines, data types and formats presents a challenge to publish, share and reuse data.
- It is difficult to create standards for the diversity of data types/formats and facilitate their adoption within interdisciplinary collaborations.
- It is uncertain which data types would be useful as reference data.
- Data analysis may require specialised skills or training that can be a barrier to interoperability and collaboration (e.g., Life-cycle assessment, computational modelling).
- Data is not always deemed valuable by its creator and is, therefore, not made openly available for reuse.

Institutional & data stewardship

- Lack of funding and financial sustainability for data and data stewardship initiatives.
- Collaborations with industry for funding or other resources may not be viable due to the nature of the information (e.g., requiring farmer consent) or regulations (e.g., government employees cannot promote a particular vendor or group).
- Grant funding faces challenges of identifying and justifying end-users and beneficiaries of agricultural data.

Governance & ethics

- Lack of attribution to data creators which leads to power imbalances (e.g., researchers in the Global North using data generated in the Global South).
- Ensuring the rights of Indigenous Peoples are respected, enabling them to set the conditions under which their traditional knowledge and cultural practices are recorded, stored and shared (see the [First Nations Principles of ownership, control, access and possession \(OCAP\)](#) and [CARE Principles](#).)
- Prioritising the distribution of collective benefit (see OCAP and [FAIR Principles](#)).
- Negotiating ongoing consent for data reuse beyond the original intention of its collection which pertains to the value that third-parties can gain by using a farmer's data.
- Anonymising personal/identifiable information about farms to enable data sharing or reuse.

PARTICIPATING GROUP & WORKSHOP LEAD*

[Improving Global Agricultural Data \(IGAD\) Community of Practice](#)

Workshop lead: [Cynthia Parr](#)

[Outputs: Wheat Data Interoperability Guidelines, Ontologies and User Cases. Recommendations from the RDA Wheat Data Interoperability Working Group](#)

[39 Hints to Facilitate the Use of Semantics for Data on Agriculture and Nutrition. Recommendations from the RDA Agrisemantics Working Group](#)

See [community group card](#)

*The workshop lead collected challenges, solutions and initiatives in preparation for the workshop and explained them during the workshop on behalf of their group.

SOLUTIONS TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES

- Gain support from funding agencies and decision makers, and identify funding agencies to support agricultural data initiatives.
- Disseminate RDA outputs internationally and increase visibility of IGAD's work (e.g., authoring position papers).
- Engage community representatives from the Global South.
- Collaborate with producers and private sector.
- Raise awareness and capacity for data sharing and stewardship.
- Create, share, socialise and promote standard policies by which data are curated, described and documented across stakeholders.
- Develop open tools for [meta]data handling.
- Work with data collectors/creators and data end-users from the outset of research activities (E.g., engage with farmers from initial stages of designing tools or databases).

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY

Collect case studies to demonstrate the benefits of open agricultural data. Collect real-world examples of good agricultural data management practice and showcase the practical implementation of [FAIR](#), [CARE](#) and [TRUST](#) principles. Such case studies may provide the basis for setting standards within agricultural subdomains.

Capacity building for digital literacy within the Global South. Develop and initiate skills training and capacity building for data management, sharing and reuse in collaboration with the [CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries](#).

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY cont'd

Identify and attribute agricultural data reuse. Organise a hackathon ([Kaggle competition](#)) to identify uses of agricultural data in scholarly literature using machine learning.

Identify and pursue public-private partnerships to tackle data challenges. Collaborate with commercial organisations to fund and deliver agricultural projects.

Create an RDA Working Group to develop ontologies and semantics for FAIR data in agriculture in collaboration with IGAD and [CGIAR](#).

RDA GROUPS/ACTIVITIES OF INTEREST

- [Agrisemantics WG](#)
- [Wheat Data Interoperability WG](#)
- [Capacity Development for Agriculture Data WG](#)
- [Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems' Data IG](#)
- [CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries](#)
- [Evaluation of Research BoF](#)
- [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [Vocabulary Services IG](#)
- [Persistent Identification of Instruments WG](#)
- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Sensitive Data IG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#)
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#)

INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST

- [GO FAIR](#)
- [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#)
- [CGIAR](#)
- [Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations \(FAO\)](#)
- [Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition \(GODAN\)](#)
- [FAIRagro \(NFDI Germany\)](#)
- [DataPLANT \(NFDI Germany\)](#)
- [AgBioData](#)
- [INTA Digital \(Argentina\)](#)
- [AgroPortal / DEMETER Agriculture Information Model](#)
- [National Agricultural Producers Cooperatives](#)
- [Agricultural Data Coalition](#)
- [Association of Public and Land Grant Universities \(APLU\)](#)
- [Global Biodiversity Information Facility \(GBIF\) data standards](#)
- [Biodiversity Information Standards \(TDWG\)](#)
- [FAO Agrovoc](#)
- [AgGateway](#)
- [Meridian Institute](#)
- [ITU E-Agriculture](#)
- [Open Technology Ecosystem for Agricultural Management \(OpenTEAM\)](#)
- [LiteFarm](#)
- [Digital Green](#)

- [Digital Ag Hackathon by Cornell Institute for Digital Agriculture \(CIDA\)](#)
- [Farm foundation Hackathon](#)
- [Agricultural Research Data Network Interoperability Conference](#)
- [CODATA Agricultural Task Group](#)
- [ISO Strategic Advisory Group on Smart Farming](#)
- [IEEE Standards and Projects for Agriculture](#)
- [Recommendations and Capacity Development Resource Kit - RDA Capacity Development for Agriculture WG output](#)
- [GEO Data Management Principles](#)
- [Advancing Data Justice Research and Practice 2021 report GPAI Paris Summit](#)
- [Community-Based Research & Data Justice Resource Guide 2022 UBC ORICE, and Gender+ Collective](#)
- [Ethical Data Management: Why It Matters and How to Make Fair Use of Data in a Digital World \(in Spanish\)](#)
- [Farm Data Management, Sharing and Services for Agriculture Development, Rome, Italy](#)
- [GEOGLAM](#)

WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

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For more information about the RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop series, please contact Community Development Manager, Connie Clare (connie.clare@rda-foundation.org)

To become a member of the RDA, register [here](#)